

Supplementary Material

**Low-Power Upconversion in Poly(Mannitol-Sebacate) Networks with
Tethered Diphenylanthracene and Palladium Porphyrin.**

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Figure S1. ¹H NMR spectrum of poly(mannitol-sebacate) pre-polymer with a feed ratio of 1:2 (mannitol: sebacate acid).

Figure S2. Emission spectrum of a solution of PdmP (10^{-5} M) and DPA(CH_2OH) $_2$ ($2 \cdot 10^{-3}$ M) in DMF upon excitation with a HeNe laser at 543 nm. The solution was degassed by argon purging for 20 min to reduce oxygen quenching in the medium.

Figure S3. Absorption spectrum of supernatant solution from soaking upconverting Poly(mannitol-sebacate) (PMSE) film for 24 h at r.t. in DMF.

Figure S4. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) traces of elastomer comprising PMSE, PdmP and DPA(CH₂OH)₂. This experiment was recorded under nitrogen at heating rate of 10 °C/min.

Figure S5. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) thermogram of the PMSE elastomer showing second heating cycle. Recorded from -50 °C to 200 °C with heating rate of 10 °C/min under nitrogen atmosphere.

Figure S6. Emission spectrum of the upconverting PMSE film upon excitation of laser at 543 nm, the upconverted delayed fluorescence (black line) was showed between 400-520 nm and the radiative decay (red line) of PdmP was showed between 630-720 nm.

Figure S7. Absorption emission spectra and fluorescence emission spectra of DPA(CH₂OH)₂ dissolved in DMF (2.6 mM) before (t= 0) and after heating in a vacuum oven at 140 °C with a pressure of 3-4 bar for 72 hours (t= 72h). The fluorescence emission was recorded upon excitation of the light source at 370 nm.